

SYNTHESIS OF 6-HYDROXYCOUMARIN-4-ACETIC ACID

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Quinol has been condensed for the first time with acetone dicarboxylic acid, and a fairly good yield of the condensation product viz., 6-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid has been obtained. The identity of this compound has been established through some of its typical derivatives. The dimethyl ether of quinol has been condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid under similar conditions, the product being 6-methoxycoumarin-4-acetic acid.

Quinol was found to react very feebly when Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1606) tried to condense it with acetone dicarboxylic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid with a view to synthesising 6-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid, and even when the acetone dicarboxylic acid was replaced by its diethyl ester, only a very small yield of the ethyl ester (m. p. 174-76°) of 6-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid could be obtained. No reference could be found in literature to the preparation of the acid itself either by hydrolysis of this ester or by any other method of synthesis.

In the course of our investigation relating to the constitution of the $\beta\beta$ -diaryl glutaric acids (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1948, Part III, p. 30) it was observed that quinol condensed easily with acetone dicarboxylic acid in the presence of 75% sulphuric acid according to the method described by Dixit and Gokhale (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1934, 3, 80) and a fairly good yield (25%) of 6-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid was obtained.

The other expected product, viz., $\beta\beta$ -di-2 : 5-dihydroxyphenylglutaric acid, however, could not be isolated.

The acid (I) was crystallised in silky white needles from hot water and melted at 186° with decomposition. It does not give a distinct coloration with FeCl_3 . By decarboxylation at the melting point it changes to the known 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (m. p. 245°) which gives an acetate (m. p. 136°) (Pechmann and Boesche, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2731) and a benzoate (m. p. 139°).

The acid (I) was also converted into its (i) acetate, m. p. 183° (decomp.), (ii) benzoate, m. p. 220° , (iii) methyl ester, m. p. 172° , and (iv) ethyl ester, m. p. 180° . The esters give a green coloration with FeCl_3 in alcoholic solution. The acid (I) cannot be converted into 6-methoxycoumarin-4-acetic acid by ordinary methylation as it is found to be rather unstable in strong alkaline solutions which rapidly develop a dark colour on exposure. Hence, the above methoxy derivative (m.p. 181° , decomp.) was indirectly obtained in small quantity by condensing the dimethyl ether of quinol with acetone dicarboxylic acid in presence of 75% sulphuric acid. This condensation also did not yield the other expected products, viz. (i) β -2 : 5-dimethoxyphenylglutaconic acid, and (ii) $\beta\beta$ -di-2 : 5-dimethoxyphenylglutaric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—Anhydrous citric acid (50 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (90 c. c., *d* 1.8) at 60° - 65° till the effervescence of carbon monoxide subsided. The mixture was then cooled (5° - 10°) and ice (10 g.) was gradually added to it with shaking without allowing the temperature to rise. Quinol (22 g.) was then added in small instalments and the mixture was kept overnight in a cool place. It was then poured on crushed ice (200 g.). The yellow granular solid which separated on stirring and scratching, was filtered, treated with a strong solution of sodium bicarbonate, the solution shaken with ether and then acidified with HCl. A white solid separated which crystallised from boiling water in silky needles, m. p. 186° (decomp.), yield 5 g. It formed an insoluble copper salt and gave a brownish coloration with FeCl_3 in alcoholic solution. (Found: Equiv., 219; C, 59.82; H, 3.90. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$ requires equiv., 220; C, 60.0; H, 3.64 per cent).

6-Acetoxy coumarin-4-acetic Acid.—6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (1 g.) was refluxed with acetyl chloride (10 c. c.) on a water-bath for an hour. On pouring the mixture on ice a yellow liquid separated which solidified on keeping overnight. This crystallised from alcohol in silky needles, m. p. 183° (decomp.), yield 85%. (Found: Equiv., 261; C, 59.4; H, 3.88. Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$: Equiv., 262; C, 59.54; H, 3.82 per cent).

Benzoyl Derivative of 6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (1 g.) was dissolved in dry pyridine (10 c. c.) and benzoyl chloride (1 g.)

added in small quantities with shaking. The mixture was kept for 4 hours and poured in dilute (1:1) HCl. A small amount of a yellow solid separated on keeping overnight. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in long prismatic needles, m. p. 220°, yield 20%. (Found: Equiv., 322; C, 66.46; H, 3.8. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$: Equiv., 324; C, 66.7; H, 3.7 per cent).

Methyl Ester of 6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (1 g.) was dissolved in dry methyl alcohol (10 c. c.) and the solution was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. On cooling the solution, the ester separated in yellowish needles, which crystallised from methyl alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 172°, yield 90%. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.35. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$: C, 61.54; H, 4.27 per cent).

Ethyl Ester of 6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—It crystallised from alcohol in short yellowish needles, m. p. 180°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 62.63; H, 5.22. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{12}O_5$: C, 62.90; H, 4.84 per cent).

6-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.—6-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (1 g.) was heated at its m. p. in a paraffin bath until decarboxylation was complete. The resulting product was washed with a solution of sodium bicarbonate, and boiled with alcohol (animal charcoal). Yellowish prisms, m. p. 245°, yield 60%. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 4.75. Calc. for $C_{10}H_8O_3$: C, 68.2; H, 4.55 per cent).

6-Acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin.—6-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with acetyl chloride (8 c. c.) on a water-bath for one hour. On pouring the mixture in cold water a solid separated which was filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol as white silky needles, m. p. 136°, yield 80%. (Found: C, 66.0; H, 4.8. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$: C, 66.06; H, 4.59 per cent).

Benzoyl Derivative of 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was prepared in a similar way as the benzoyl derivative of 6-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid and obtained as a slightly crimson coloured solid which was filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from dilute acetic acid as white shining needles, m. p. 139°, yield 1.1 g. (Found: C, 72.70; H, 4.63. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$: C, 72.85; H, 4.285 per cent).

6-Methoxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—Anhydrous citric acid (25 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (45 c. c., d 1.8) until the elimination of carbon monoxide was complete. The mixture was cooled (5°-10°) and ice (10 g.) added carefully. Quinol dimethyl ether (12 g.) was added to it in small instalments with constant shaking. The shaking was continued for one hour and the reaction mixture was kept overnight at the room temperature. It was then poured on crushed ice (100 g.). On keeping overnight a small quantity of a yellowish powder separated.

It was filtered, washed several times with water and dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution. The solution was shaken with ether and acidified with HCl. The solid which separated was filtered, washed and crystallised from boiling water in yellow shining needles, m. p, 181° (decomp.), yield 5%. (Found : Equiv., 233.5. C, 61.69 ; H, 4.42. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$: Equiv., 234 ; C, 61.54 ; H, 4.27 per cent).

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